

WP2: National policy, legal and service frameworks

Psychosocial Support for Promoting Mental Health and Well-being among
Adolescent Young Carers in Europe: ME-We project, Grant Agreement number
754702

Country-specific report (case study) Switzerland

Source: <http://schweizer-kantone-orte.websieb.info/>

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Categories	Results
Specific legislation	In Switzerland, no specific legislation protecting and supporting young carers and their families exists.
Non-specific legislation National level	<p>Federal Constitution of the Swiss Confederation of 18 April 1999 (Status as of 1 January 2018), https://www.admin.ch/opc/en/classified-compilation/19995395/index.html (Bundesverfassung der Schweizerischen Eidgenossenschaft vom 18. April 1999, SR 101) Art. 11 Protection of children and young people Children and young people have the right to the special protection of their integrity and to the encouragement of their development (paragraph 1). They may personally exercise their rights to the extent that their power of judgement allows (p.2). Targeted age group: children (minors up to 18)</p> <p>Swiss Civil Code of 10 December 1907 (Status as of 1 January 2018), https://www.admin.ch/opc/en/classified-compilation/19070042/201801010000/210.pdf (Schweizerisches Zivilgesetzbuch vom 10. Dezember 1907, SR 210); Child and adult protection law (Kindes- und Erwachsenenschutzrecht) Targeted age group: children (minors up to 18) and adults</p> <p>Convention on jurisdiction, applicable law, recognition, enforcement and cooperation in respect of parental responsibility and measures for the protection of children (Hague Convention on the Protection of Children), https://www.admin.ch/opc/de/classified-compilation/20061344/index.html Übereinkommen über die Zuständigkeit, das anzuwendende Recht, die Anerkennung, Vollstreckung und Zusammenarbeit auf dem Gebiet der elterlichen Verantwortung und der Massnahmen zum Schutz von Kindern (Haager Kinderschutzübereinkommen, HKsÜ), in Kraft getreten für die Schweiz am 1. Juli 2009, SR 0.211.231.011 Targeted age group: children (minors up to 18)</p>

	<p>Social Security Law, in particular Art. 29septies Federal Law on Old Age and Survivors' Insurance (AHVG), SR 831.10, https://www.admin.ch/opc/de/classified-compilation/19460217/index.html</p> <p>Provides financial funding for families (care credits), thus indirectly relieves the burden on young carers as well.</p> <p>Targeted age group: adults</p>
<p>Enactment of legislation National/cantonal level</p>	<p>In Switzerland, the cantons and communities are responsible for the enactment of the legislation e.g. the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC). In order to get the legislation into force, the cantons and the communities have to translate it. The federation does a lot of recommendations how the cantons could do it but it is very diverse because of the differences in the individual cantons.</p>
<p>Enactment of legislation Regional level</p>	<p>None mentioned</p>
<p>Changes in legislation</p>	<p>Legal provisions for carers in Switzerland are still developing.</p> <p>Regarding changes in legislation, there is a paradigm shift from the welfare approach to the right based approach. Today, it is very important that children are informed about their rights and this has changed. Children and parents are being more and more informed.</p> <p>Changes in legislation were achieved by private and political initiatives so far.</p>
<p>Specific policy and service frameworks National level</p>	<p>Action plan for support and respite of relatives providing care from December 5th, 2014 https://www.bag.admin.ch/bag/de/home/strategie-und-politik/politische-auftraege-und-aktionsplaene/aktionsplan-pflegende-angehoerige.html (Unterstützung für betreuende und pflegende Angehörige, Situationsanalyse und Handlungsbedarf für die Schweiz, Bericht des Bundesrates vom 5. Dezember 2014)</p> <p>Targeted age group: all carers, including minors</p> <p>Federal Research Programme "Support and Relief Offers for Carers 2017-2020" https://www.bag.admin.ch/bag/de/home/strategie-und-politik/nationale-gesundheitspolitik/foerderprogramme-der-fachkraefteinitiative-plus.html .</p> <p>Targeted age group: all carers, young carers are explicitly included in the research.</p>

<p>Non-specific policy and service frameworks</p> <p>National/cantonal level</p>	<p>Children and youth policy: https://www.bsv.admin.ch/bsv/de/home/sozialpolitische-themen/kinder-und-jugendfragen.html</p> <p>Defined in an umbrella concept, Health Promotion Switzerland has a uniform basis for the cantonal action programmes (KAP). It contains four modules and eight principles which the cantons use as a basis for their KAPs. https://gesundheitsfoerderung.ch/kantonale-aktionsprogramme/basisinformationen/dachkonzept.html</p> <p>Counselling services (respite, support), Canton of Vaud, https://www.espaceproches.ch/</p>
<p>Non-specific policy and service frameworks</p> <p>Local level</p>	<p>Youth counselling in Zurich, https://www.stadt-zuerich.ch/sd/de/index/familien_kinder_jugendliche/jugendliche/jugendberatung.html; http://jugendberatung.me/jugend-blog/</p> <p>Family counselling services, e.g. in the the Canton of Zurich: Children and Family service –Centers (kjz). In almost every Canton there might be public services for young people and for families.</p>
<p>Enactment of policy and service frameworks</p> <p>National level</p>	<p>Four action fields in the “National Action Plan for Carers Support and Relief” from December 5th, 2014, https://www.bag.admin.ch/bag/de/home/strategie-und-politik/politische-auftraege-und-aktionsplaene/aktionsplan-pflegende-angehoerige.html :</p> <p>Action field 1: Better information and better data (including young carers) Action field 2: Respite options - Access and Quality (including young carers) Action field 3: Reconciling work and family care (young carers older than 16 years) Action field 4: Care leave for parents with children who are sick (field 4 does not apply to young carers) or alternative support options</p>
<p>Changes in policy and service frameworks</p>	<p>Action plan for support and respite of relatives providing care: This emerged from a political push from the Swiss Parliament and of the Federal Council as part of the agenda Health 2020 (http://www.euro.who.int/de/health-topics/health-policy/health-2020-the-european-policy-for-</p>

	<p>health-and-well-being). This started in 2011 and at the end of 2014 the action plan was adopted.</p> <p>In 2014 young carers were not included in the action plan. However subsequently, there was a petition from the Parliament addressing this exclusion of the situation of minors providing care for their relatives. Now the Swiss Federal Council explicitly mentions the situation of children who care for family members and plans to gather more information on this situation with a project that started in 2017 and that will continue until 2020.</p>
<p>Recognition of young carers</p>	<p>Young Carers are not specifically defined in the law.</p> <p>Carers Day: October 30</p> <p>https://www.redcross.ch/de/rotkreuz-entlastungsdienste/entlastungsdienste-fuer-pflegende-angehoerige/tag-der-pflegenden</p> <p>http://www.pflege-entlastung.ch/waadt</p>
<p>Key strengths</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Flexibility: legislation and services are regionally flexible which can make innovations easier. Regional variation is important since there are different needs in different regions - In general, basics needs in Switzerland are well supported - How legislation is translated into practice is set by law and this is well established in Switzerland - Child protection authorities are generally working well and in an interdisciplinary manner and usually there are established networks (health, education, protection, etc.) even on a regional level - In general, legislation is very clear and there is a lot of literature, e.g. in the area of parents of a disabled child - There is no discrimination, meaning that all the persons have equal rights - The Federalist system allows a “Me-too-effect”: when one canton has good practices, then other cantons will adopt them sooner or later
<p>Key limitations National level</p>	<p>General limitations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Young carers do not exist as a specific social group in Switzerland, and therefore they are not specifically addressed by support programmes - The legal provisions for caregiving only relate to working carers and supporting a balance between work and informal care. They do not take into account young carers who are studying or who are doing an apprenticeship - Terminology within the Swiss Civil Code such as “best interest of the child” is very open to interpretation. However, this is also a chance because it allows acting and reacting on an individual situation within individual circumstances. - The topic of young carers is addressed only for very specific issues, e.g. financial or insurance issues, but the need for support of young carers is not considered - Laws, policy frameworks, and even some associations working with carers do not use an age-appropriate language

	<p>for young people, so the information may not be accessible to young carers, who do not have an adequate level of literacy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of coordination between the different legal systems (e.g. social security system, family law, medical law, child protection, etc.) - The healthcare system in Switzerland is expensive and this can affect vulnerable groups like young carers - Situations where children are responsible for the caring of their parents are kept private in the family - Patients who are filed (e.g. for a mental illness) might face problems in the future, e.g. if their child has been seen late at night on the street. File references by their nature have a long lifespan and there is a risk that such data will later be used for purposes or in contexts other than those for which they were originally created. <p>Limitations of child protection authorities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There is a marred history with respect to child protection in Switzerland, because in the last century it has happened that children were forced out of their families in the name of child protection under circumstances that would be seen from the perspective of today as grave violations of the rights of these children and their families. - It is difficult to identify young carers, because the authorities (e.g. child protection services) are not promptly notified by healthcare institutions - Child protection services can be frightening for families because they intervene in case of child abuse. It seems like there is nothing between “invisibility” of young carers and “mistreatment” (and consequently the intervention of child protection services) - Child protection services generate high financial costs to the society - The measures of child protection legislation can only be taken if the child's best interest is threatened, it is not sufficient that a child's best interest is not being fully achieved - Child authorities have limited powers, it is only when there is no other way to avoid the threat to the child's best interest that the child protection authority can remove the child from the family - The child protection authority only becomes involved if the problems of the young carer are visible - The outcomes of the interventions taken by child protection authorities are not really evaluated and are therefore not known, therefore it is not clear if this is the right kind of help that young carers and their families need <p>Limitations of the Action Plan:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Action Plan for support and respite of relatives providing care does not consider children as carers. It may be more relevant to young adult carers since it includes topics on financial benefits and insurances.
<p>Key limitations Regional level</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Swiss health system is not well developed for in-house support, e.g. family carers do not receive much financial support

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Differences between how cantons implement the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child, despite the recommendations coming from the Federation
<p>Evaluation of the current situation</p> <p>National level</p>	<p>Evaluation of the current situation in general:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In the legislation the topic of young carers is quite overlooked and the perspective of the young carers is not sufficiently taken into consideration - Soft laws in Switzerland are quite important because they are not enforced by legislation but rather they are based on commitment - The Social Security Law is extremely important because it provides financial funding for families which can take the pressure off young carers - Young carers should be protected because they are in a role that might threaten their right to education and their development. Also the right to play and the right of spare time are very important for children and their development. - The awareness on young carers is low, but in Switzerland there is a solid legal system with a lot of protection for the children - There is a social problem, defined as “parentification”, which means that the children are acting like “the parents of their parents”. This is harmful for the child and can lead to negative consequences - Young carers’ right to education are not really being fulfilled - Hospitals may not routinely ask if a patient has children - Switzerland's general approach is to provide good conditions to prevent poverty - Many stakeholders are involved and should collaborate, e.g. schools, NGOs, health professionals, etc. Legislation and policy frameworks need to look more at structures and conditions for allowing professionals to work well together - Programmes are starting to think more about children as carers and including them as a vulnerable group. Special programmes are well established for young carers who care for parents with mental health conditions <p>Evaluation of the current situation regarding child protection authorities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The child protection system is very well established and working well in Switzerland but the outcomes of child protection measures are not really known - Child protection authorities have the aim to help vulnerable children; however, this can be viewed as the state invading the private rights of families. Help may be not forthcoming however due to a climate of avoidance of such situations - In Switzerland there is a debate on child protection authorities: some think that children are not “property” of their parents and the State has an obligation to intervene, while others think that child protection authorities have too much power. This is due to the interpretation of terms in the Swiss Civil Code like “best interest of the child”

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The child protection authority often work with young carers where the issue is parental ill-health but seldom where children care for parents with a physical illness. <p>Evaluation of the current situation regarding the recognition:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - At the moment, caregiving is an important topic in Switzerland. Therefore, this is the right moment to raise awareness on the topic of young carers
<p>Attitudes to existing policy responses National level</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The legal provisions might not really help the people affected, who might need more specific support (e.g. financial support for respite) - The UN Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC) could be used as the basis for developing specific legislation or services - Child protection involvement in relation to young carers could be very good but has to be thought about carefully - There are a lot of discussions about the costs of child protection services
<p>Attitudes to existing policy responses Regional level</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Current efforts made towards supporting young carers at the moment are coming mainly from the cantons
<p>Suggested changes</p>	<p>Suggested changes to the legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It seems not necessary to have a specific legislation for young carers, because there are not specific laws for every group of people in need. However, in Switzerland there are many legal provisions that can be a basis for new frameworks or services addressing young carers - Existing legislation, policy and service frameworks could be extended to include young carers - In the Action Plan it is suggested to modify the labor law. Young carers who are working could then have a day off when needed <p>General changes suggested:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Awareness on the topic of young carers must be raised. A possible solution is through NPOs or NGOs, which might have some ideas that could be supported by state funding. Everyone should be informed about this topic - Young carers and their needs should be recognised by applying the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child. However, it must be acknowledged that the best interest of the child is different for every child - Young carers should be defined, so that they can identify themselves as young carers - The communication (of legal provisions, policies, service frameworks, but also communications from associations working for carers) should be adapted and be more age-appropriate for young people

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Professionals should be trained and made aware of the topic - Changes should be made within a Federal programme, but also on a cantonal level - It would be important to know which are the results of measures taken by child protection authorities - The existing programmes should be made more visible and also be more understandable for young people - The issue of young carers must be systematically addressed. More data is needed in order to find solutions to make these children visible - The different legal systems involved (e.g. social security system, family law, medical law, child protection, etc.) should be better coordinated - Parents should be better supported in realizing the situation of their children (including the specific needs) and be motivated to look for specific help and care - Stigmatisation must be avoided - Collaboration between health services, counselling services and child protection services should become self-evident (under consideration of the right to privacy)
<p>Future goals and hopes National level</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Have more data to make better decisions on the type of support needed by young carers and their families and in this way make evidence-based changes to the legislation - Recognise the importance of the role played by family carers - Young carers should be recognised by the health system, by schools, etc. in order to receive the support they need and they should be involved in this process - Look at every child's situation individually and hear the voices and opinions of young carers - Strong political commitment, as well as support of administration and private initiative like NPOs or NGOs - More awareness, everyone should be informed on the topic - Awareness and commitment from professionals in the health, social and educational fields - More support to young carers both on a political level and in a practical ways (e.g. helpline) - Identification of young carers, who also need to identify themselves as carers - A "life-course-approach", including all life-phases, because in every life-phase one can be a carers - Involvement of young carers and their families, give them the possibility to share their opinions about what their needs are and what kind of support can help them - More support (e.g. from social services) in hospitals for patients and their children